

Mitigating Plastic Litter Culture in Enugu, Nigeria: The Theatre Intervention Paradigm

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Abstract

After several decades of plastic production, the non-biodegradable nature of plastics has become a major concern for humanity. Consequently, the plastic scourge is increasingly becoming a widespread environmental challenge globally, including in Enugu State, Nigeria. This multidisciplinary study focuses on climate change, indigenous awareness, and ecological relationships in Enugu, Nigeria. The paper aims to connect theatre, creativity, and environmental management in critical discourse to examine the role of theatre and recycling in tackling the plastic litter problem, which is an environmental issue in Enugu. The impact is often characterised by erosion, drought, flooding, human, economic, and financial losses, among others. Reference was made to Greg Mbajiorgu's play *Wake up Everyone*, to illustrate the dangers of environmental pollution. An experimental play, "Snippet of Hope," was also used to raise awareness among some communities in Enugu State about the importance of recycling and plastic waste management. Results show that many residents participating in the experimental play demonstrated significant improvements in their waste management practices. As a result, it was recognised that theatre plays a vital role in changing residents' attitudes from improper littering to proper waste disposal practices. The study employs a qualitative research methodology, utilising content analysis and an experimental research design. It is grounded in ecological humanism and environmental literacy theories. The study concludes that theatre can evolve from simply being a medium of entertainment into a problem-solving art, by promoting campaigns addressing environmental challenges and advocating for environmentally friendly alternatives to help preserve the environment.

Keywords: *Plastic Waste, Climate change, Environment, Enugu State, Non-Biodegradable.*

INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation, corruption and economic crisis are some of the major global concerns affecting humanity and negatively impacting the climate. In the editorial of the Vanguard Newspaper of August 18th, 2012, (Mbajiorgu, 2012a) explained that, "this rapid dismantling of our environment is engendering the extinction of species, loss of biodiversity, decline of marine stock, shortage of food and ecosystem imbalance". Globally, the climate is being raped daily through activities that are harmful to the environment. In Africa, many people like Orakpo (2012, 10) have attributed the reason for the degradation to illiteracy, ignorance and religion. She argued that "phrases like climate change, global warming, carbon emission and greenhouse gases have become part of our daily vocabulary, yet so many people do not know what they are all about". She added that "many religious groups view climate change from the point of view of the bible and attribute it to the end-time, saying that the end of the

world as we know it, is here". Orakpo (2012). Scientists, on the other hand, contend that "the changes occur as a result of daily activities of man, which affect the environment negatively (Ibid). The researchers submit that one of the major contributors to environmental degradation is the introduction of polymers, especially the synthetic type, from which plastic materials of different kinds are made. Since the formation of the Earth over 4.5 billion years ago, elements like Carbon, Hydrogen, Oxygen, and Nitrogen have been combining to form complex molecules (NASA Science, June, 2024).

"Plastic is a synthetic or semi-synthetic lightweight, hygienic and resistant material produced through different organic polymers such as nylon, polyvinyl chloride, polyethene, etc., which can be moulded and utilised in many varieties of ways and applications"(UNEP Report, 2022-2023). Plastic, being one of the world's most used materials, is regarded as technically lightweight and cheap. As its name suggests, it emanated from the Greek word *plastikos*, which loosely translates to 'capable of being shaped or moulded' or to grow or form. Thus, it can adopt any shape or form. The problem of plastic materials does not lie in its usage because it is seemingly harmless, but in its end-of-life management, which is the improper disposal of materials made from it, especially the single-use plastics. Each day, new products are being manufactured in addition to already existing ones and the more plastics are produced, the more the environment is exposed to harm. Lending his voice on the increase in plastic production, (Mbajiorgu, 2020b: Forward) noted that "despite the scourge of plastic waste in our world, the demand for plastic is soaring...Plastic demand is projected to triple if we do not change our consumption patterns. Our oceans and aquatic animals endure and suffer from most of this overzealous dependence on plastics".

Before the industrial revolution, which grossly encouraged the massive production of plastics, the environment was not as polluted as now. This is partly because plastic was not as common as it is in contemporary times. In Africa for instance, before the age of the industrial revolution, leaves were used to wrap food items for preservation. People cooked, drank and ate with wooden cups, clay and earthen pots, plates etc. Ochuba and Okechukwu (2011), assert that "Common waste produced during the early ages was mainly ashes and human & biodegradable waste, which were released back into the ground locally with minimal environmental impacts". Soon after, plastics became more common and more sought after and started replacing other materials like leaves, clay, paper, mud and raffia, etc.

Presently, many people globally are experiencing different kinds of health defects that are associated with the use of plastics. Cancer, metabolic disorder, reduced fertility and skin discolouration are some of the illnesses associated with plastics (<https://www.genevaenvironmentnetwork.org>). The amount of plastic waste being dumped into the oceans poses a big danger to marine wildlife and to humanity. Buttressing this point, (Guterres (2024), stated that "by the year 2050, there will be more plastics than fish in the ocean. This does not augur well for the marine life that we must protect". Similarly, the ozone layer is depleting daily; and human activities such as burning of used plastics and improper disposal of plastics do not in any way help to better or preserve the environment.

Theoretical Framework

Ecological Humanism takes the view that human beings are capable of transforming their societies so as to promote the flourishing of both humanity and nature and advocates that humanity and nature should work together to deal with the current ecological crisis, like the degradation of the natural environment (<https://www.log.culturalecology.info.org>). Morris

(1922) ascribed the pioneers of Ecological Humanism to "three intellectual giants, namely, Lewis Mumford, Rene Dubos and Ron Chepesiuk". In "his work *Environmental Literacy: Knowledge For a Healthier Public*; Chepesiuk (2007) posits that;

Human beings in society directly or indirectly affect the environment either positively or negatively, whether it is through eating food preserved in plastic packs or improper disposal of plastic waste etc. Each day, people make decisions that affect the environment, whether they are getting ready to go to work, preparing dinner or buying products for the house (<https://www.pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>).

From Chepesiuk's perspective above, the environment is directly or indirectly influenced by human actions. The way we choose to behave on matters concerning the environment will significantly impact it. A collective consciousness, awareness, and discipline regarding what is needed for a safer space and environment would greatly assist human beings in addressing issues related to climate change. When examining the study through the frameworks of Ecological Humanism and environmental literacy, it highlights the relationship between society and the environment. Furthermore, environmental literacy involves individuals' awareness and consciousness to undertake responsible actions that protect habitats and promote environmentally friendly communities. It is on this note that the researchers advocate for using drama and theatre as mediums to raise awareness in Enugu state about how their actions, inactions, and lifestyles intersect with the environment. Environmental educators believe that the earlier people begin learning waste management, the better it is for them, their families, and society, because good environmental knowledge helps individuals understand how to make decisions and take actions that foster a safer and more positive environment.

METHODOLOGY

The paper adopts a qualitative research methodology, utilising an experimental research design and content analysis approach to examine the content of the study play, *Wake Up Everyone*, and an Experimental playlet titled "Snippet of Hope." Content analysis, as explained by (Drisko and Maschi 2017), asserts that qualitative content analysis as a research technique is used to make "replicable and valid inference from texts to contexts of their use." It is a methodology for systematic content analysis, descriptively examining the manifested ideas while seeking to conceptualise them. The adoption of Drisko and Maschi's approach for this study includes interpreting the relationship between humans and the environment. Additionally, existing literary and sociological knowledge on plastic litter culture, recycling, and waste management is applied to clarify the arguments. An experimental research design is employed to facilitate the development of the experimental play, aimed at raising awareness in Enugu communities about the importance of recycling. These approaches will enable the research to go beyond the mere surface of the study play and playlet, aligning with our focus on ecological humanism and environmental literacy, to identify the ecological challenges faced by the communities Enugu State.

Brief Evolution of Plastics

Since the dawn of history, humankind has endeavoured to develop materials offering benefits not found in natural materials. The development of plastics started with the use of natural materials that had intrinsic plastic properties, such as shellac. The next step in the evolution of plastics involved the chemical modification of natural materials such as Rubber, Nitrocellulose, Collagen and Galalite. Their plasticity makes it possible for plastics to

be moulded, extruded or pressed into solid objects of various shapes. This adaptability, plus a wide range of other properties, such as being lightweight, durable, flexible, and inexpensive to produce, has led to its widespread use. A key breakthrough came in 1907, when Belgian-American Chemist Leo Baekeland created Bakelite, the first real synthetic, mass-produced plastic.

Since Baekeland's creation, many new plastics have been realised and developed, offering a huge range of desirable properties, which can be found in many homes, offices, factories and vehicles. (Leighton, 1942), is of the view that "The need to preserve scarce natural resources made the production of synthetic alternatives a priority". In consideration of the dangers that plastic litter portends in the environment, the study shall examine plastic use culture in Enugu State.

An Overview of Plastic use Culture in Enugu State

Enugu State, in South East Nigeria, is predominantly a commercial, industrial, and educationally privileged state with numerous notable higher institutions located within it. Some of these institutions include the University of Nigeria, Nsukka; Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT); Godfrey Okoye University (GOU); among others, in addition to several colleges of Education, polytechnics, and a Law School. Notable industries in the area include Innoson Nigeria Limited, Wilson Group Nigeria Limited, Nigeria Breweries, ANAMMCO Motors, Emerite Asbestos, Willson Nigeria Limited, Peace Group of Companies, and others. The state also hosts many commercial banks, parastatals, churches, and major markets. The "coal district in Enugu covers over 270,000 hectares of the coal basin and has supported the largest amount of commercial mining in the past. In addition to two underground mines, there are a total of 36 drill holes drilled in the area". (<https://www.ejatlas.org>). "Plastic is used daily in several applications like greenhouses, mulch coatings, wiring, packaging, films, bags, containers, PET bottles, beverage bottles, and biomedical, among others" (World Economic Forum Report, 2023).

Despite the pollution caused by mining and the production of plastic-based products, which are manufactured, purchased, and used in various institutions, industries, and households in Enugu State, the battle against plastic pollution remains in its early stages. Farmlands, water bodies, and drainage systems are being adversely affected due to improper plastic waste disposal and management. "In 2004, the then administration in Enugu State established the Enugu State Waste Management Authority (ESWAMA) to replace the defunct Enugu State Environmental Protection Agency (ENSEPA), which failed to meet the challenges of the modern waste management system, as waste dumps were situated close to residential areas, markets, farms, and roadsides" (Ochuba and Okechukwu, 2011). ESWAMA has recorded minimal success in controlling the improper disposal of plastic waste across the 17 Local Government Areas of the state. Confirming this, Assia and Nahla (2024) observed that "Authorities struggle to contain and properly dispose of waste, as evidenced by overflowing bins, roadside litter, and the proliferation of illegal dumps." It was observed that various types of used plastic materials are discarded indiscriminately daily, as many communities lack suitable disposal systems, and many individuals do not follow government directives on waste management.

During a fact-finding mission by the researchers, it was discovered that many people in the 17 Local government areas in Enugu state are not aware of the dangers inherent in littering the environment with used plastics, nor are they aware of the process of recycling In some

areas, like the capital city of Enugu state, ESWAMA waste disposable baskets and bins are visible with wastes scattered all around the bins, while in other communities, there are very few waste bins put in place by the government for waste collection. In many places like the major market (*Ogbete, Ogige, Akwata, Kenyetta*, etc), schools, public places etc, wastes are indiscriminately dumped in open places, with used plastics in larger proportions. See **FIG. 1**.

Sanika and Rashmi (2019), speaking about policies designed to mitigate the scourge, explained that "various governments across the world have come up with creative policies to mitigate the plastic threat." Etakong (2018) added that "the most promising solutions being adopted globally, which have proven successful, include a complete ban in Rwanda, a plastic tax in Ireland, and voluntary initiatives in Australia.

Meanwhile, in countries such as Bangladesh, Ghana, Rwanda, Washington DC, Uganda, South Africa, and Tanzania, the prevention of plastic waste generation has been achieved through taxation or bans on the use of certain types of plastics." Notable scholars have observed that attaching a price tag to plastic waste could transform the problem into an opportunity, as well as reduce plastic consumption. Ogwo et al. (2013) submit that "deposit-refund systems are considered the most applicable and suitable instruments through which externalities, such as the recyclability of packaging, can be regulated."

In light of the above, (Adegboye, 2021), a civil society expert under the aegis of Global Alliance for Incinerator Alternatives GAIA, "called on the federal government to ban single-use plastics with effect from the year 2021, as against 2028 date contained in the proposed National Policy on Plastic Waste Management and urged them to start with banning of Styrofoam, micro beads and carrier bags as they have no economic value or recycling potentials" (Vanguard, 19 November, 2020).

The group maintained that "outlawing plastic use in Nigeria, will provide an avenue to clean the environment by reducing the impact of plastic pollution in its natural habitats and wildlife". The researchers, therefore, suggest that one of the viable ways to rid the environment of used plastics is to use the avenue of Theatre to sensitise communities in Enugu through Theatre for Development dramatisations on how to source for used materials, and recycle them into usable costumes, accessories, props for theatre performance purposes, and usable items for the home.

It can serve as a viable alternative for theatre props and accessories, especially in educational and non-educational theatres. (Ambrieres 2019) in his work titled *Plastics Recycling Worldwide: Current Overview and Desirable Changes...* explained that "recycling is the best solution for processing plastic waste because it limits environmental impact and generates significant socio-economic gain". Below are a few figures on human consumption of plastic. In the same study, the forum asserts that:

1 million plastic bottles are purchased every minute in the world;

2 million single-use plastic bags are distributed every day in the world;

500 million plastic straws are used every day in the United States;

57 million plastic straws are used every day in Canada (World Economic Forum Report, 2022).

Mbajjorgu(2011c, Preface), in the preface to his work *Plastics, Plastics Everywhere...*, revealed that “more than one million seabirds as well as over a hundred thousand sea mammals die every year because of the overwhelming presence of plastics in our oceans and seas. According to (Knight 2009),

apart from the steady accumulation of plastic junk, there is another looming problem - where we get our plastics from in the first place. Currently, most of them come from oil and gas. But when these finite sources eventually run out, the obvious solution will be to go back to the days of Parkes and Goodyear and look to biology.

The market should be looking for more bio-derived plastics that are chemically identical to the plastics we use now.

Perspective on Recycling

Recycling essentially entails reusing, reprocessing, salvaging and converting discarded, worn out or non-usable materials and wastes into usable items. It is a process of recovering or recycling waste materials into new materials and objects, which can be channelled into the same use as conventional ones. The holy writ recorded that "Adam and Eve had no clothing or materials to cover their nakedness. They sewed fig leaves together and made a body covering for themselves with it" (Genesis 2011, 3:7), and that was the first recorded recycled costume made by man. Thus, in verse 21, “The Lord made garments of skin for Adam and his wife and clothed them” (Genesis 2011, 3:21). This act of God for Adam and Eve, goes to show that creativity is also part of God’s design from the beginning, in line with the process of recycling.

Recycling has been a common practice for most of human history as far back as the era of Plato in 400 B.C., when he wrote about the importance of recycling and sustainability (<https://www.peelscarpmetalrecycling.com>). Archaeological studies of ancient waste during that period show less household waste. This implied that more waste was being recycled in the absence of new materials. There is evidence that during those pre-industrial times, scrap bronze and other metals being collected in Europe were melted and redesigned for reuse. Paper recycling was first recorded in 1031BC when Japanese shops sold used paper. (<https://www.nerc.org>)

In the area of theatre, there is no definite period of when recycling of costumes and accessories started; rather, man’s creativity and quest to find a means to an end by picking up items in his environment and creating clothing, props and accessories from them may have triggered the process of recycling. Ever since Adam, Eve and Plato, man has been using varied types of materials for props, costumes and accessories for productions. For instance, the early men were able to extract the teeth of dead animals and recycle them into necklaces, head and arm bands, while the skin of animals was recycled into clothes and furs for coverage and protection.

The need to look inwards for alternative sources of costume materials, set pieces, accessories and props which goes beyond the use of conventional fabrics and tools to include but not limited to recyclable items in form of cardboard sheet, bottle corks, leaves, wood particles (saw dust), worn-out bags, plastics, feathers, quills, animal skin, horn, tusk and skin of animals, discarded costumes, polythene, polypropylene materials, jute materials, feathers, nylon, wool and paper mash etc. All these materials, among others, can be recycled and reprocessed to create, design and produce stage props, costumes and accessories like clothes, jewelry, fans, walking sticks, bags, wigs, head headgear among others, for the theatre as well as usable materials for home and offices.

Processes of Recycling of Plastic Wastes into Theatre and Household Items.

There are diverse types of items that can be recycled out of plastic waste into different designs. For this research, selected plastic wastes (plastic bottles, spoons, plastic bottle covers, foam, wire, polythene and band) (**FIG. 2**), were recycled into Theatre props (staff and white seat), costumes, head crown (accessories). For the seat, plastic bottles and covers (see **FIG. 6 and 7**) were gathered and placed together, then a round board was placed at the bottom to secure it. After that, foam was used to pad up the plastic bottles together to form a seat. A cover for the seat was sewn with white polythene and used to finally wrap up the set pieces (white seat). See **FIG. 5**.

For the costume, staff and crown, the costume was sewn with a white and green polythene material. For the black hair band, sticks were attached and glued to the black plastic wire band to form a head crown. See **FIG. 4**. For the staff, green plastic bottles were moulded together to form a long staff with plastic spoons glued on the staff. After that, the glue was allowed to dry in order to hold the plastic spoons firmly. See **FIG 3**. Furthermore, **FIG. 2**, contains samples of the plastics used for recycling.

The set piece was made with a board, plastic, bottle covers and glue. First, the drawing was sketched on the board with a pencil, and glue was applied to the plastic cover and placed on the drawing to get the desired design. Finally, the glue was allowed to dry. See **FIG. 3**.

Theatre as a Tool for Social Change

Theatre is one of the most acceptable art forms which embodies many theatrical elements. As a medium for communication, it transcends the functional barriers of language, traditional and cultural differences, using the creative potentials of both visual, verbal and non-verbal channels. The role of art is to serve as a conscience to the soul of man by guiding, informing, sensitising and prescribing better options for a positive and improved way of life. Theatre, as a performance art, embodies these characteristics as it uses the medium of storytelling through dialogue and mimetic actions to bring desired change to any society. Environmentalism, on the other hand, is concerned with the protection of the environment, especially from harmful human activities. The paper will attempt to access essential areas of Environmentalism in relation to the experimental play "Snippet of Hope". Theatre engages the attention of the people through a dramatic presentation of problems. It makes the audience see their problems in fresh and critical ways. In Enugu state, for instance, theatre is being used to address some the problems affecting the society, ranging from cultural conflicts, to developmental problems like gender based violence, exploitation etc. The researchers, through an experimental play; "Snippet of Hope" exhibit how drama can serve as a tool for a social campaign and this is portrayed through the characters of Sanda, Bona, Tolu and Chairman.

Analysis of the Experimental Play "Snippet of Hope"

The play "Snippet of Hope" is an environmentalist eco-terrestrial dramatisation of contemporary society. It is a one-scene play that depicts how drama can serve as a tool for social campaigning. The play opens on a street corner, where we see Bona, one of the characters, attempting to collect plastic litter, which he makes a living from by selling most of the waste in exchange for money. He also recycles some into beautiful wares. Tolu believes that plastic waste is useless, viewing it solely as environmental waste that should be eliminated. Bona tries to make Sanda and Tolu recognise the importance of these wastes and what can be created from them. Ultimately, Sanda and Tolu begin to see the significance of plastic waste

as Bona showcases his beautiful wares (costumes, props, set pieces, etc), made from the waste, alongside the money he earned from selling some of the recycled items.

Assessment of the Experimental Play and Audience Response

The experimental play “Snippet of Hope” was written and directed by the researchers. The scriptwriting and data collection took two weeks. Before the performance, the researchers conducted fact-finding visits to several communities in Enugu, collected the necessary data, and made some observations. The play, as an advocacy scenario, was staged successfully, conveying its intended message to the audience (communities).

A platform was created for the audience to share their reviews, and at the end of the performance, there was a highly interactive post-performance discussion. Audience members responded positively, expressing the impact they gained from the play. Eze (2023) affirmed that, “The play is really impactful. I have always known how to dispose of waste properly but have never given much thought to waste management and recycling.” I am inspired to consider recycling or encouraging others to recycle plastic waste.” This indicates that many people are not fully informed about waste management and therefore pay little attention to their environment. Most audience members also confirmed that the performance served as an enlightenment and eye-opener. Many admitted to having been victims of plastic waste mismanagement but decided to change their approach for the better after watching the play. Ede (2024), in her response, said she will "contribute towards the eradication of plastic waste by storing them safely and reusing them in an artistic manner like she saw in “Snippet of Hope.”

Discussion/Allusion to Mbajiorgu's *Wake Up Everyone*

According to (Eze 2023), "climate change requires an interdisciplinary approach; thus, drama is a crucial tool for exploring its intricacies and communicating its messages in a produced and urgent way than any other means of communication". Mbajiorgu's *Wake up Everyone* (2011) is a drama on climate change and a wake-up call for everyone to have a rethink on how we treat the environment. In Ndoli local government area, Edwin Ochonkeya receives the sum of three hundred million naira in addition to oil companies bankrolling his election. This is as a result of the untimely death of his father through oil spillage. On the other hand, Prof. Aladinma, who is an activist and an environmental protection crusader, warns the community about an impending environmental disaster if they do not retract their steps concerning the way they mismanage the environment and his warning is captured thus,

The soil and the rivers have become unproductive because of the chemicals and oil we pour on them. The flood and the erosion we experience are caused by our senseless attempts to reclaim wetlands and our blockages of original water channels and drainages...The problem of our world was created by man (Mbajiorgu 2011c, 15)

The people of Ndoli land, continue to ignore the warning. The chairman refuses to give out three hundred million naira as counterpart fund for the construction of a dyke in Ndoli land, a project that would have helped to save their degraded land. Shortly after the warning, the whole community started feeling the impact of environmental degradation and drought, and it forced many of them to flee from their homes in search of safety, a calamity that would have been averted if they had all listened when the protagonist Prof. Madukwe Aladinma, a retired professor of agriculture, was giving them the warning sign. The play is a response to environmental challenges of poor litter culture, bad governance, and deforestation, among others.

CONCLUSION

Climate change has emerged as one of the most pressing global challenges, driven by increased human activity and industrial growth, which significantly harm human health and the environment. The use of plastic-based materials and their disposal methods is causing considerable damage to the environment, including Enugu State. (UNEP Report, 2018), cautions that "unless we rethink the way we produce, utilize and manage plastics, we will won't be able to cope with the quantity of waste we generate". In many parts of Enugu state, the control of plastic waste has been ineffective.

In light of the above, this study attempts to determine how Theatre intervention has helped to mitigate plastic litter culture in communities in Enugu. Results showed that Theatre and drama have helped the residents of selected communities in Enugu state, to embrace a more proactive waste mechanism. As Apeh, Anigbogu and Apeh(2022) observe, "People indiscriminately dump waste in the open, particularly on the streets, roads, residential compounds and as a consequence, discomfoting to residents due to the offensive, stinking odour emanating from those sites. Thereby, exposing them to various kinds of diseases".

Therefore, serious attention is necessary to address this menace and reduce associated risks. Findings show that the method of waste management in Enugu does not make provision for recycling. "The process remains largely limited to collection, transport, and disposal, neglecting sorting and recycling". World Health Organisation (WHO) recommends that the best solution to the plastic scourge is prevention through awareness creation about its adverse effects on health and the environment.

This highlights the potential for intervention via Ecological Humanism and Environmental literacy using drama and theatre, given their capacity to offer meaningful solutions to global issues. Through this approach, the study suggests that raising awareness about the plastic problem and promoting recycling of used plastics into usable items—whether at home, in offices, or theatres—is a viable method to mitigate the scourge.

The researchers experimented with used plastics such as spoons, polythene, wire, plastic bottles, and covers, and were able to produce items like hairbands, a walking staff, a seat, a hand fan, and costumes. Using the Environmental Literacy theory, which advocates the use of skills, knowledge, and awareness to address environmental issues, and drawing on Mbajiorgu's play – *Wake Up Everyone* – as well as the experimental play "Snippet of Hope," the paper suggests that the problem of climate change and plastic pollution can be tackled if enough awareness is cultivated among people.

This can be achieved through using drama and theatre to educate about the impacts of improper plastic disposal and promote proper recycling methods. Adding their voices, Apeh, Anigbo and Apeh (2022) recommend that "ESWAMA as a regulator should sponsor and organise periodic public awareness campaigns on radios." By this, Apeh et al. are referring to theatre intervention and other communication mediums.

The researchers argue that since it is clear that plastic plays a significant role in our daily lives, scientists should work to develop bioplastics derived from plant crops instead of fossil fuels. The government should incorporate Theatre for Development to sensitise residents of Enugu on the best waste management mechanisms.

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APPENDIX

Fig 1: Pictures of plastic waste litter

Fig 2: Plastic materials used by the researchers to recycle costume and props and crown

Fig 3: Steps used to achieve recycled head crown, staff, costume & prop

Fig 4: Fitting of the costume and props made with recycled plastic waste by the researchers

Fig 5: Actors on stage for the experimental play ‘snippet of hope’ using some of the recycled props

Fig 6: Materials used by researchers to in making a set piece

Steps used by the researchers to make a set piece

Fig 7: Recycling of plastic bottles to make a seat